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public class TicTacToe {
    private char[][] board;
    private char currentPlayer;

    public TicTacToe() {
        board = new char[3][3];
        for(int i=0; i<3; i++) {
            for(int j=0; j<3; j++) {
                board[i][j] = '-';
            }
        }
        currentPlayer = 'X';
    }

    public boolean placeMark(int row, int col) {
        if (row < 0 || row > 2 || col < 0 || col > 2) {
            return false;
        }
        if (board[row][col] != '-') {
            return false;
        }

        board[row][col] = currentPlayer;

        if (checkWin()) {
            System.out.println("Player " + currentPlayer + " wins!");
            return true;
        }

        switchPlayer();
        return true;
    }

    private void switchPlayer() {
        if (currentPlayer == 'X') {
            currentPlayer = 'O';
        } else {
            currentPlayer = 'X';
        }
    }

    private boolean checkWin() {
        for (int i = 0; i < 3; i++) {
            if (board[i][0] != '-' && board[i][0] == board[i][1] && board[i][1]
== board[i][2]) return true;

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        if (board[0][i] != '-' && board[0][i] == board[1][i] && board[1][i]
== board[2][i]) return true;
    }

    if (board[0][0] != '-' && board[0][0] == board[1][1] && board[1][1] ==
board[2][2]) return true;
    if (board[0][2] != '-' && board[0][2] == board[1][1] && board[1][1] ==
board[2][0]) return true;

    return false;
}

public static void main(String[] args) {
    TicTacToe game = new TicTacToe();

    game.placeMark(1,1);
    game.placeMark(0,0);

    game.placeMark(0,0);

    game.placeMark(0,2);
    game.placeMark(1,0);
    game.placeMark(2,0);
}
}
```